

ŠPORT KOT PRIZORIŠČE NASILJA: ANALIZA POJAVNIH OBLIK, DEJAVNIKOV IN ODZIVOV

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Povzetek

Namen: Namen raziskave je proučiti pojavne oblike, dejavnike in razsežnosti nasilja v športu ter analizirati, kako različni akterji – športniki, trenerji, starši in institucije – prispevajo k njegovemu vzdrževanju ali preprečevanju.

Metodologija: Študija temelji na kvantitativnem pristopu. Podatki so bili zbrani z anketnim vprašalnikom med 115 športniki, ki so poročali o svojih osebnih izkušnjah z nasiljem v športnem okolju.

Ugotovitve: Rezultati kažejo, da je več kot polovica sodelujočih športnikov doživela vsaj eno obliko nasilja. Najpogosteje se nasilje povezuje s pretirano tekmovalnostjo in pritiskom na dosežke, kar spodbuja agresivno vedenje v ekipah. Nasilje je pogostejše v kontaktnih športih ter na mladinskih tekmovanjih, kjer starši in trenerji pogosto izvajajo neprimeren pritisk. Ugotovitve potrjujejo, da gre za kompleksen družbeni pojav, ki zahteva celostne rešitve.

Omejitve: Omejitve raziskave izhajajo iz relativno majhnega in omejenega vzorca ter možnosti subjektivnega doživljanja nasilja, kar lahko vpliva na zanesljivost in posplošljivost rezultatov.

Praktične in ali družbene posledice: Raziskava poudarja potrebo po etičnem vodenju, ustreznem izobraževanju trenerjev in staršev ter krepitvi kulture spoštovanja. Ugotovitve lahko služijo kot podlaga za oblikovanje preventivnih programov in smernic za zmanjševanje nasilja v športu.

Izvirnost: Raziskava prispeva k razumevanju nasilja v športu z združevanjem empiričnih podatkov in analizo različnih akterjev, ki vplivajo na športno okolje. Posebna vrednost raziskave je v osvetlitvi vloge pritiskov in tekmovalne kulture, zlasti v mladinskih tekmovalnih kategorijah.

Ključne besede: nasilje, šport, vrste nasilja, dejavniki, etika

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SPORT AS A SCENE OF VIOLENCE: ANALYSIS OF MANIFESTATIONS, FACTORS AND RESPONSES

Summary

Purpose: *The aim of the research is to examine the forms, factors, and dimensions of violence in sports and to analyze how different actors—athletes, coaches, parents, and institutions—contribute to its persistence or prevention.*

Methodology: *The study is based on a quantitative approach. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire administered to 115 athletes who reported their personal experiences with violence in the sports environment.*

Results and Conclusions: *The results indicate that more than half of the participating athletes experienced at least one form of violence. Violence is most associated with excessive competitiveness and performance pressure, which foster aggressive behavior within teams. It occurs more frequently in contact sports and in youth competitions, where parents and coaches often exert inappropriate pressure. The findings confirm that violence in sports is a complex social phenomenon requiring comprehensive solutions.*

Research limitations: *The limitations of the research stem from the relatively small and specific sample, and the potential subjectivity in perceiving violence, which may affect the reliability and generalizability of the results.*

Practical and/or Social implications: *The study highlights the need for ethical leadership, appropriate education of coaches and parents, and strengthening a culture of respect. The findings can serve as a foundation for developing preventive programs and guidelines aimed at reducing violence in sports.*

Originality: *This research contributes to the understanding of violence in sports by combining empirical data with an analysis of various factors influencing the sports environment. Its value lies in shedding light on the role of performance pressures and competitive culture, especially in youth competitive categories.*

Keywords: *violence, sport, types of violence, factors, ethics*

JEL Classification: Z29 Other Sports Economics

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Introduction

Violence in sport represents not only a challenge within sporting arenas but also a complex social phenomenon with far-reaching consequences for individuals, communities, and the integrity of sport itself. Although sport is traditionally associated with values such as discipline, cooperation, and fair play, various forms of violence—physical, psychological, verbal, and even symbolic—still persist. These manifestations are influenced by multiple factors, including competitiveness, social and cultural pressures, and media representation. Previous research has shown that violence in sport can arise from both structural and interpersonal dynamics, ranging from aggressive play and spectator behaviour to institutional abuse and exploitation (Grant, 2006; Spaaij, 2014). The normalization of aggression and the glorification of victory often blur the line between acceptable competitiveness and harmful behaviour. Such dynamics challenge the ethical foundations of sport and call for comprehensive preventive measures.

The purpose of this paper is to analyse the manifestations, causes, and consequences of violence in sport, and to explore how athletes perceive and experience violence in their sporting environments. The study combines a theoretical review of the concept of violence with an empirical survey among athletes from various disciplines. The findings aim to contribute to a better understanding of the complexity of violence in sport and to support the development of strategies for its prevention and mitigation.

Violence in sport

Definition of violence

Violence is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that has accompanied human societies throughout history. It can be physical, psychological, verbal, or structural, and it occurs in every cultural, social, and economic context. Although the term is widely used, scholars agree that there is no single, universally accepted definition. The concept of violence depends largely on cultural norms, moral values, and the balance of power between individuals or groups.

From a psychological perspective, Sigmund Freud (1930) viewed violence as an expression of basic human instincts, particularly the drives of aggression and destruction. He argued that aggression is part of the human unconscious and often a reaction to frustration. In contrast, Skinner (1953) explained violence as learned behaviour, maintained through reinforcement or reward—people repeat aggressive acts when they have previously led to success or control.

From a sociological standpoint, Pierre Bourdieu (1991) introduced the concept of *symbolic violence*, referring to subtle and often invisible forms of domination exercised through language, cultural norms, and social institutions. This form of violence is not physical, but it reinforces inequalities and power hierarchies. Max Weber (1919), on the other hand, described violence as the “legitimate use of physical force” monopolised by the state—a view that situates violence within systems of authority and social order.

Despite these differences, most definitions share several common elements:

- Intentional harm—violence involves behaviour that deliberately causes or threatens physical, psychological, or emotional injury.
- Power imbalance—it arises when one party uses power, control, or influence to dominate another.
- Violation of integrity—violence undermines an individual’s autonomy, dignity, and sense of safety.

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) defines violence as “*the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or a group or community, that results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, maldevelopment, or deprivation.*”

This comprehensive definition highlights that violence is not limited to physical acts but includes psychological and structural forms of oppression. In summary, violence can be understood as both a behavioural act and a social relation, embedded in systems of power and inequality. Its manifestations depend on context, but its essence remains the same—an intentional act of harm that violates human dignity and autonomy.

Types of violence

Violence can manifest in many interrelated forms that often overlap and reinforce one another. Although typologies may vary, most authors distinguish between psychological, physical, verbal, sexual, economic, and online violence (Novak, 2013; APA, 2018; Council of Europe, n.d.; Safe.si, n.d.). Each type differs in its means of expression and consequences but shares the common element of an abuse of power.

Psychological violence

Psychological or emotional violence refers to behaviour that causes mental distress, fear, or degradation without the use of physical force. It may include intimidation, manipulation, humiliation, control, isolation, and threats. According to the American Psychological Association (APA, 2018), repeated psychological abuse can lead to long-term mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, or post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Because it leaves no visible marks, it is often underestimated, yet it can be as destructive as physical aggression.

Physical violence

Physical violence involves intentionally causing bodily harm to another person. This can include punching, kicking, slapping, choking, and other forms of physical assault. It is often the most recognisable form of violence, but it is not necessarily the most common. Studies show that physical violence can lead to serious health problems, including chronic pain, injury, and even death (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.).

The main purpose of the perpetrator is not only to cause physical pain, but also to limit the victim's self-determination. Such violence demonstrates differences in social power and seeks to enforce certain demands. In addition, physical violence is often accompanied by other forms of violence, such as psychological and economic violence. For example, victims of physical violence are often also victims of psychological violence, which further exacerbates their mental and emotional distress. Physical violence can have long-term consequences that affect the quality of life of victims, including reduced ability to work, social isolation and permanent disability (Council of Europe, n.d.).

Verbal or verbal abuse

Verbal violence, sometimes called verbal abuse, encompasses speech or expression intended to humiliate, insult, or intimidate another person. It undermines the victim's self-esteem and self-worth through ridicule, accusations, threats, or derogatory language. Although it does not involve physical harm, verbal aggression can have serious psychological and social effects, fostering fear, shame, and emotional withdrawal (Žontar, 2024). In the sporting context, it often appears in the form of shouting, insults, or verbal humiliation by coaches, teammates, or spectators.

Sexual violence

Sexual violence includes any non-consensual sexual act, attempt, or unwanted contact that involves coercion, manipulation, or abuse of authority. It encompasses rape, sexual harassment, molestation, exploitation, and trafficking (Police, 2013). The psychological consequences—feelings of guilt, shame, and social stigma—often persist long after the physical injuries heal. Women and children are the most frequent victims, but men may also experience sexual abuse, particularly in hierarchical or closed environments such as sports teams or training camps.

Economic violence

Economic violence occurs when one person unjustifiably controls or limits another's access to financial resources, property, or employment opportunities (ZPND, 2008). It is a form of coercion that deprives victims of independence and decision-making power. While most common in family settings, it can also appear in sport—for example, when athletes' earnings or sponsorships are mismanaged, withheld, or used as a means of manipulation by managers or institutions (Hostnikar, 2014).

Online violence

Online or cyber violence refers to any act of aggression, harassment, or intimidation carried out through digital means—social networks, messaging platforms, or online communities. Common forms include cyberbullying, hate speech, doxxing, or the non-consensual sharing of intimate images. Victims of online violence often experience psychological distress like that caused by face-to-face abuse. The anonymity of the internet amplifies hostility and reduces accountability (Safe.si, n.d.).

These forms of violence frequently overlap—for example, physical aggression may be accompanied by verbal humiliation or economic control. Their impact extends beyond immediate harm, affecting victims' mental health, social participation, and overall sense of security. Understanding the diversity and interconnectedness of violence is essential for developing effective prevention strategies, particularly in environments such as sport, where competitiveness and hierarchy can normalise aggression.

Forms and example of violence in sport

Violence in sport appears in multiple forms and across all levels of competition. It may arise between athletes, coaches, referees, spectators, or institutions. Each form of violence carries distinct characteristics, yet all share the misuse of power and the erosion of fair play (Grant, 2006)

Physical violence by athletes against athletes

Physical violence in sport can have a significant impact on the health and well-being of athletes and on the overall sporting culture. Violence occurs between athletes themselves, but coaches, referees and organisers may also be involved. In a sporting environment where competitiveness and pressure to succeed are high, the significance of physical violence is often overlooked or minimised, leading to the normalisation of such behaviour. The consequences of such acts are not only physical but also psychological, as they can lead to long-term trauma, burnout and even the decision of athletes to give up their sporting activities (Vveinhardt et al., 2019).

Here are just a few of the many examples that have been reported in the media:

Example 1: On 30 June 2013, Otávio Jordão da Silva refereed an amateur football match in Pio XII, Maranhão. He sent off player Josemir dos Santos Abreu, who refused to leave the pitch and attacked one of the referees. Abreu hit da Silva, prompting him to pull a knife from his pocket and stab him several times. Abreu died on the way to hospital. When Abreu's supporters learned of his death, they sought him out, stoned him to death, and cut his body into pieces. (Djau and Brumfield, 2013).

Example 2: During the 2006 World Cup final, French footballer Zinedine Zidane headbutted Italian player Marco Materazzi. The incident occurred after Materazzi allegedly insulted Zidane's family. Zidane was sent off for this action, which had a significant impact on the outcome of the match. Zidane later explained that his reaction was the result of provocation that deeply affected him, while Materazzi admitted that he had used inappropriate language but claimed that he did not intend to provoke such a reaction. The incident sparked extensive debate about sportsmanship, provocation on the field, and the consequences of violence in sport. Zidane received a three-match suspension, and the incident remains one of the most memorable moments in World Cup history (FIFA, 2024).

Example 3: Mike Rice, coach of the Rutgers Scarlet Knights basketball team, was fired after a video was released showing his violent behaviour during training sessions. The video, which was broadcast on ESPN, showed Rice pushing, grabbing and throwing balls at players during training sessions and using homophobic slurs. The incident sparked widespread criticism, including responses from New Jersey Governor Chris Christie and the President of the New Jersey Assembly, who called for Rice's dismissal. Rice was initially suspended for three games, fined \$50,000 and ordered to attend anger management classes. However, following the release of the video and mounting criticism at the state and national levels, Rutgers University decided to dismiss him. Rice later publicly apologised for his behaviour and admitted that he had let down his players, the university and his family (ESPN, 2013).

Example 4: During a football match between Chelsea and Swansea City in January 2013, Eden Hazard, then a 22-year-old Belgian striker, got into a conflict with 17-year-old ball boy Charlie Morgan. Swansea was leading 2-0, and Morgan was trying to delay the game by lying on the ball when Hazard tried to get to it. Hazard, in anger, kicked the ball boy in the stomach, which attracted a lot of attention and criticism. Referee Chris Foy gave Hazard a red card, which meant that Hazard missed the match and was suspended for three matches (Marca, 2024).

Sexual violence

Sexual violence in sport is a serious and often overlooked problem that affects many athletes, regardless of their age, gender or level of competition. This form of violence includes various types of abuse, including physical, psychological and emotional violence, which can be perpetrated by coaches, referees, teammates or even fans. Sports environments, which often promote a culture of power and authority, can create a space for this type of abuse. Many athletes, especially younger ones, are afraid to speak out about abuse for fear of retaliation, loss of career opportunities, or disapproval from their teammates. In many examples, victims believe that they are to blame for the abuse, which further complicates the situation (Marks et al., 2012; Parent and Demers, 2011).

Example 1: Larry Nassar was a long-time doctor for the US gymnastics team and was accused of abusing numerous young gymnasts over a period of several years under the guise of treatment. The victims included top athletes such as Simone Biles, Aly Raisman and McKayla Maroney. The abuse took place when the girls were young and often vulnerable, which allowed Nassar to take advantage of his authority and the trust the athletes had in him. When the victims spoke out, Nassar's behaviour came to light, triggering a major investigation. In 2018, he was sentenced to 175 years in prison (BBC News, 2024).

Example 2: At the 2023 Women's World Cup, held in Australia and New Zealand, the Spanish team won the gold medal. A controversial incident occurred at the medal ceremony when Luis Rubiales, president of the Spanish Football Federation, kissed footballer Jenni Hermoso. As Rubiales handed out the medals, he approached Hermoso and kissed her on the lips, sparking immediate backlash. Hermoso later said that she was uncomfortable and had not consented to the intimate contact. Her statement triggered an immediate media response, and Luis Rubiales resigned 10 days after the incident (Reuters, 2024).

Violence in the mass media

The mass media play an important role in shaping public opinion about sport, athletes and events, but this influence also has a dark side. Violence perpetrated by media discourse often manifests itself in the form of sensationalism, negative stereotypes and personal attacks, which can have serious consequences for athletes and the sporting community in general (MediaSmarts, 2022).

One of the most obvious ways in which the media can have a violent impact on sport is through sensationalist reporting. In order to attract attention and increase viewership, the media often focuses on scandals, controversies and the personal lives of athletes. Such coverage often leads to a distorted representation of reality and diminishes the importance of athletic success and the discipline required to achieve top results. Athletes find themselves under constant scrutiny, which can lead to stress, anxiety and burnout. Very often, sports news and commentary use metaphorical language that glorifies and promotes physical conflict – language that fans typically enjoy because it is vivid and exciting. Commentators describe games using terms such as "body slam", "taking them down" and "going for the jugular" (MediaSmarts, 2022; Crisp a Kroll business, 2023).

The media often perpetuates negative stereotypes about women, ethnic minorities and the LGBTQ+ community in sport. Female athletes are too often portrayed solely through the lens of their appearance, rather than highlighting their talents and achievements. This not only diminishes their contribution to sport, but also perpetuates inequality in society. Similarly, athletes from ethnic minorities often face racial stereotypes that diminish their success based on their race or cultural affiliation (Hoffman, 2018).

In recent years, a new phenomenon has emerged – "cancel culture", where athletes who express their views or make a mistake are quickly condemned and excluded from public life, with no chance of rehabilitation. This approach leaves no room for growth, learning and forgiveness, which is contrary to the fundamental values of sport (Choo, n.d.).

Example 1: During the COVID-19 pandemic, Novak Đoković became the target of intense media scrutiny and criticism for his decision not to get vaccinated. His stance sparked extensive reporting that often went beyond objective analysis and turned into verbal abuse. When he announced that he would not be vaccinated, numerous media outlets began publishing articles labelling him "irresponsible" and "selfish". Commentators often accused him of putting his own interests above the health of others, leading to numerous personal attacks on his integrity and character. Terms such as "deception" and "anti-social behaviour" were used, further escalating tensions. Following his deportation from Australia, some media outlets described the event as a "shameful episode," contributing to the negative image they wanted to create of him (BBC News, 2022).

Example 2: In 2021, Naomi Osaka, a Japanese tennis star and one of the best players in the world, announced that she would not be attending press conferences at the Roland Garros tournament. The reason for this decision was concern for her mental health, as she stated that press conferences are often detrimental to the mental health of athletes, especially after difficult defeats. Osaka's decision sparked a wave of criticism and pressure from the mass media, which labelled her move unprofessional and irresponsible. The Roland Garros tournament fined her and warned her that she could be excluded from the tournament if she did not attend press conferences. Due to mounting pressure and criticism, Osaka decided to withdraw from the tournament (CBC Sports, 2021).

Fan violence

Fan violence in sport can have far-reaching consequences for everyone involved, including athletes, clubs, leagues and local communities. This phenomenon often manifests itself in the form of physical assaults, vandalism, racism and other forms of aggression, which can be directed at opposing fans, players or even the police. Despite the fact that sport is intended to bring people together and entertain, violence among fans is often normalised and legitimised in the context of rivalries (Ward, 2002).

The consequences of such violence are not only immediate, but can also affect the long-term health of sports culture and create an environment of fear. Sports organisations and governments are working to reduce violence by introducing strict laws and protocols, but the challenge of how to effectively manage this issue remains. It is crucial to develop positive models of fan behaviour and community involvement that would contribute to a safer and more inclusive sporting environment (Ward, 2002).

Example 1: One of the most famous examples of fan violence occurred in 1985 during a match between English club Liverpool and Italian club Juventus in the European Cup final in Brussels. This event is known as the "Brussels Massacre". During the match, Liverpool and Juventus fans clashed, leading to a violent incident in which 39 people, mostly Italian fans, died and more than 600 were injured. The conflict erupted when Liverpool fans attacked the stands where Juventus fans were sitting, causing panic and a stampede. This tragedy had far-reaching consequences for football. Following the incident, UEFA banned English clubs from participating in European competitions for five years (Mohapatra, 2015a).

Example 2: In November 2004, during an NBA game between the Indiana Pacers and the Detroit Pistons in Auburn Hills, Michigan, a notorious incident occurred. As the game was coming to an end, a fan in the crowd threw a drink at Ron Artest while he was lying on the scorer's table. Artest ran into the crowd in anger and attacked the fan, sparking a mass brawl between fans and players. This incident, known as "Malice at the Palace," led to lengthy suspensions for several players and caused major changes in security protocols at NBA games (McKeone, 2024).

In addition to the aforementioned and detailed forms of violence in sport, it is also worth highlighting other forms that are less common but no less serious. These forms of violence, although perhaps less visible, can have equally serious consequences for individuals and sports communities as the more obvious and media-exposed forms. These forms include:

- Racism and ethnic violence in sport.
- Economic exploitation and forced labour of athletes.
- Homophobia, violence related to the LGBTQ+ community.

Racism and ethnic violence in sport

Racism and ethnic violence in sport threaten the foundations on which sport is built: respect, cooperation and equality. Despite the progress we have made in the area of diversity and inclusion, racist attacks and discrimination still occur in many sports. Athletes from minority groups are often the targets of offensive comments, condemnation and even physical violence, either from opponents or from fans. This type of violence affects not only individuals, but also the entire sporting culture. When athletes face racism, it can lead to a loss of motivation, reduced performance and even the decision to end their career. At the same time, such an environment can deter young talents from minority groups who fear they will not be accepted or that they will face discrimination (Anderson, 1996).

Example 1: A notorious example of racist violence occurred at a football match in Italy in 2018. Kalidou Koulibaly, a Senegalese defender playing for Napoli, was the target of racist insults from Inter Milan fans. During the match, fans made monkey noises and threw bananas onto the pitch, causing widespread outrage in the sporting community (BBC Sport, 2018).

Economic exploitation and forced labour of athletes

The economic exploitation and forced labour of athletes negatively impact the integrity of the sports industry and the well-being of athletes. Many young athletes, especially those from less privileged backgrounds, often find themselves in situations where they are exploited by agents, clubs and organisations that take advantage of their desire to succeed. These athletes often sign contracts that include low wages, long working hours and a lack of adequate protection of their rights. Forced labour in sport can take the form of athletes being subjected to inhumane working conditions, which affects their health and psychological well-being. Athletes who find themselves in such situations often work under pressure to achieve success, which can lead to burnout and long-term health problems (Coakley, 2014).

Example 1: In his autobiography, *Open*, Andre Agassi, a former American tennis player, revealed how he was forced to compete under pressure from his father, who was determined to make him a tennis champion. Agassi described how, from an early age, he was subjected to strict discipline and intense training, often against his will. His father was aggressive and often pressured Agassi to achieve success and earn the money the family needed (Agassi, 2009).

Homophobia, violence related to the LGBTQ+ community

Homophobia is a deeply rooted problem in sports culture that affects the physical and mental health of athletes who belong to the LGBTQ+ community. Sports culture is often saturated with discrimination and violence directed at individuals based on their sexual orientation or gender identity. Athletes from this community face verbal abuse, physical attacks and systemic exclusion, which limits their potential. Violence against athletes from the LGBTQ+ community is not limited to personal conflicts but is often institutionalised. In addition to direct violence from teammates, fans, and coaches, these athletes face policies and practices that prevent them from participating fully and being treated equally (European Commission, 2022; Denison et al., 2020; Symons et al. 2020).

Biological males have, on average, certain physiological advantages that can affect athletic performance. These include greater muscle mass, higher testosterone levels, greater bone density and greater lung capacity. Transgender individuals who were born as biological males and identify as females may retain certain advantages over biological females due to these physiological advantages acquired prior to transition. This is particularly noticeable in sports where strength, speed and endurance play a key role. On the one hand, we are faced with discrimination against transgender athletes who are fighting for the right to equal participation and acceptance. While on the other hand, there are concerns about fairness to biological women, who may feel that they are at a disadvantage due to the physiological advantages that transition may bring (Jones, 2020; Hilton and Lundberg, 2021).

Example 1: Greg Louganis was one of the most recognisable divers of the 1980s, known for his outstanding achievements, including gold medals at the Olympic Games. Despite his successes, Louganis faced tremendous pressure and discrimination because of his homosexuality. His identity became the subject of interest and investigation, reflecting the broader social stigma towards same-sex

orientation at the time. In 1995, Louganis publicly disclosed his HIV status, which further increased media attention. His disclosure sparked an important debate about the stigmatisation of people with HIV and how gay athletes often experience discrimination and violence. Louganis' courage and openness laid the groundwork for greater acceptance and understanding, but his story is also a reminder that many athletes still face challenges related to their identity and rights (Lindsay du Plessis, 2021).

Example 2: Caster Semenya, a South African middle-distance runner, faced extensive public and media pressure over questions about her sexuality and appearance after winning the 800-metre race at the 2009 World Championships. As doubts about her gender began to surface, the International Association of Athletics Federations (IAAF) demanded that she undergo testing, putting her under immense pressure. In some examples, the tests were so invasive that samples were taken from her, including situations where she was forced to undress. This situation sparked a huge debate about ethics and athletes' rights, especially in relation to intersex people. Semenya has become a symbol of the fight for the rights of intersex athletes, as she continues to battle against rules that limit her right to compete. Her story highlights the importance of understanding and respecting diversity in sport and the need for fair treatment of all athletes, regardless of their gender or gender identity (Ataman and Macfarlane, 2024).

Example 3: Lia Thomas, a swimmer from the United States, became the first trans woman to win a national championship at the university level in swimming. Before her transition, Thomas competed in the men's category, where she did not achieve notable results. After transitioning and starting hormone therapy, she began competing in the women's category, where she achieved outstanding results compared to her competitors. Later, new rules were introduced by World Aquatics, prohibiting transgender women who had gone through male puberty from participating in elite women's swimming competitions. Thomas appealed this rule to the Court of Arbitration for Sport, but her appeal was rejected, meaning she was not allowed to compete in the qualifiers for the 2024 Summer Olympics in Paris (ABC, 2024)

Factors contributing to violence in sport

Violence in sport does not result from a single cause but from a complex interaction of individual, social, situational, and structural factors. Understanding these determinants is crucial for designing effective prevention strategies and promoting a culture of respect and fair play.

Individual and Interpersonal Factors

At the individual level, aggression may arise from personal traits such as impulsivity, low frustration tolerance, and competitiveness. Athletes who experience high emotional arousal during competition may struggle to regulate anger, particularly when provoked or under pressure (Spaaij, 2014). Interpersonal relationships between athletes, coaches, parents, and spectators can further reinforce violent behaviour through modelling and social learning. According to the social learning theory, individuals imitate aggressive actions when they are rewarded or socially approved (UK Essay, 2017).

Verbal abuse or excessive criticism from coaches and parents can also provoke retaliation or emotional distress among athletes. Studies have shown that loyalty to a team or coach can increase tolerance for aggressive behaviour, leading athletes to perceive violence as acceptable or even necessary for success (Wanjiku, 2016).

Situational and Environmental Factors

Situational elements—such as the intensity of competition, the nature of the sport, and the immediate physical environment—play a significant role in the manifestation of violence. Sports that involve direct physical contact (e.g., football, hockey, boxing) inherently carry higher risks of aggression. The pressure to win, combined with fatigue, provocation, or perceived injustice, can trigger violent incidents on the field (UK Essay, 2017).

Spectator composition and crowd dynamics also influence the likelihood of violent behaviour. Younger and less emotionally mature fans are statistically more prone to aggression, particularly when alcohol consumption, rivalry, or poor crowd control are involved. Overcrowded and inadequately managed facilities further increase the risk of violent outbreaks. For instance, poorly controlled fan movements contributed to the Heysel Stadium disaster in 1985, when rivalry between Liverpool and Juventus fans led to the deaths of 39 people and injuries to more than 600 (BBC News, 2022; Mohapatra, 2015b).

Similarly, in 1989, a failure in crowd management at the Hillsborough Stadium resulted in the deaths of 93 people due to suffocation, again demonstrating the tragic outcomes of poor organisational control and infrastructure design (BBC News, 2022). Such events highlight the interdependence between physical environment, management quality, and human behaviour in the escalation of violence.

Socio-cultural and Structural Factors

Sport both reflects and reproduces wider social dynamics. Cultural norms that glorify toughness, dominance, and victory at all costs contribute to a climate in which aggression is normalised. Media coverage often amplifies rivalries and portrays violence as entertainment, which indirectly legitimises it among athletes and fans (Spaaij, 2014; Ward, 2002).

Economic and institutional pressures can also serve as structural drivers of violence. Professional athletes face intense expectations to perform and maintain sponsorships, while coaches and clubs are evaluated based on results. These conditions foster environments where emotional control is undermined and ethical boundaries are blurred. Additionally, weak governance structures, inconsistent disciplinary systems, and a lack of education on ethical conduct enable the persistence of violent behaviour.

Integrated Perspective

No single factor can fully explain why violence occurs in sport. It emerges through the interaction of psychological predispositions, environmental stressors, and social influences. For example, an aggressive athlete may act violently only in settings where crowd hostility, competitive tension, and institutional tolerance converge.

Therefore, strategies to prevent violence must be multidimensional—combining athlete education, coaching ethics, crowd management, and institutional accountability. Creating safer sporting environments requires cooperation among all stakeholders: sports organisations, schools, local communities, and media outlets.

Methods

Methodology and sample

The study employed a quantitative research design to examine the prevalence, forms, and perceived causes of violence in sport among athletes in Slovenia. A structured questionnaire was developed and distributed personally to athletes across multiple disciplines. The quantitative approach was chosen to enable statistical analysis of relationships between variables and to test predefined hypotheses about the presence and determinants of violence in sport.

Data collection was conducted between 10 November 2024 and 20 December 2024, ensuring that participants represented various sporting contexts and competition levels. The data were processed using SPSS software, allowing for descriptive and inferential statistical analysis.

A total of 115 valid responses were collected. Of the participants, 83% were male ($n = 95$) and 17% were female ($n = 20$). Respondents represented a range of sports, including athletics, handball, basketball, tennis, cycling, and judo. The sample was selected randomly from the researcher's network of athletes and sports clubs, ensuring heterogeneity and reducing selection bias. Although the sample was not representative of all Slovenian athletes, its diversity across different disciplines provides valuable insight into patterns of violent behaviour and experiences in sport.

Based on the theoretical framework and research objectives, the following hypotheses were tested:

H1: Athletes face violence in their sporting activities.

H2: Intense competitiveness and pressure to succeed increase the incidence of violence in sports teams.

H3: Violence in sport is more common in disciplines where competitors are expected to display a high level of physical aggression.

H4: Athletes are more exposed to violence in youth and amateur sports, where pressure from parents and coaches is often present.

Participation was **voluntary and anonymous**, and all respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and the confidentiality of their responses. No personal identifiers were collected.

The study has certain limitations. The sample size ($n = 115$) limits the generalisability of the results to the entire population of athletes in Slovenia. Furthermore, the self-reporting method may introduce **response bias**, as some participants might underreport or overreport experiences of violence due to social desirability or fear of judgment. Future studies could enhance reliability by including longitudinal designs, interviews, and data triangulation.

The methodological design provided a structured approach to exploring violence in sport through the lens of athletes' experiences. The combination of quantitative analysis and descriptive interpretation enabled a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and laid the foundation for hypothesis testing in the following sections.

Results and discussion

This section presents the findings of the empirical research and discusses them in relation to the hypotheses defined in the previous chapter. The analysis focuses on the prevalence of violence among athletes, the role of competitiveness and pressure, the impact of sport type on violent behaviour, and the influence of parents and coaches in youth and amateur sport.

First, we examined whether athletes face violence in their sporting activities. Analysis of the responses shows that 58% of athletes have already experienced violence in their sporting activities. Violence is very widespread in sport, as it occurs in various forms – physical, psychological, verbal and sexual violence. Sports competitions and training are often subject to high pressure, competitiveness and the desire to win, which can lead to tension and violence among participants. Athletes may face violence from their coaches (38%), teammates (27%), fans (19%) or even opponents (16%) (figure 1). Both physical injuries and psychological effects, such as harassment or abuse, are common problems that affect the well-being of athletes. The forms of violence experienced by the participants in the study come from players on opposing teams, coaches, teammates, referees, spectators and parents.

Figure 1: Presence of various forms of violence among athletes (in %)

We also asked them, in order to obtain more in-depth results, which factors they believe contribute most to violent behaviour in the team and whether they believe that intense competitiveness is a key factor in the occurrence of violence in their team.

Table 1 shows the results on the prevalence of violence in sports teams. Most respondents (72%) answered that violence occurs "sometimes", followed by answers that violence occurs "very often" (24%). 4% believe that violence is not present. This shows that violence is not a constant problem, but it is nevertheless present.

Table 1: Occurrence of violence in sports teams

Answer	Number of respondents	Percentage
Violence occurs very often	28	24
Violence occurs sometimes	82	7
Violence does not occur	5	4
Total	115	100

In the next part of the study, the analysis focused on the key factors contributing to violence in sport. Intense competitiveness was identified as the most influential factor (43%), followed by pressure to succeed (35%), poor leadership (17%), and other factors (5%).

The findings indicate that the atmosphere of constant rivalry and achievement-oriented goals often leads to frustration and emotional tension among athletes. Excessive pressure from coaches, teammates, or the media can increase stress levels and reduce self-control, creating conditions in which aggression is more likely to occur.

Competitiveness, particularly in team sports such as football and basketball, may encourage behaviours that prioritise victory over respect and fair play. In such environments, aggression is sometimes tolerated as a natural reaction to stress or as part of team dynamics, which can escalate into violent outbursts or interpersonal conflicts. A more detailed analysis of teams in which competitiveness is strongly emphasised could further clarify the connection between performance pressure and the emergence of violence.

Violence in sport tends to be more common in disciplines where competitors are expected to demonstrate a high degree of physical aggression. Sports such as boxing, mixed martial arts (MMA), hockey, or rugby inherently involve physical contact and, to some extent,

aggressive behaviour as part of the game itself. In these sports, aggression is often viewed as a legitimate element of strategy and performance. Such normalisation of physical dominance can blur the boundary between acceptable competitiveness and violence. Conversely, in non-contact sports, similar behaviour is generally perceived as inappropriate or unsportsmanlike.

The cultural acceptance of aggression in contact sports can therefore lead to a higher tolerance for violent acts, both during and outside competition. Previous research confirms that when aggression is integrated into the rules or ethos of a sport, it can foster an environment where violent conduct is more readily excused or even rewarded.

The analysis also focused on the extent to which athletes are exposed to violence in youth and amateur sport, where pressure from parents and coaches is often present. The study examined whether respondents had ever experienced physical, verbal, or emotional violence during these stages of their sporting careers, who the main sources of pressure or aggression were, and how frequently they encountered inappropriate behaviour from authority figures during training or competitions.

More than half of the respondents (57%) reported experiencing some form of violence—physical, verbal, or emotional—while 43% stated they had not. This suggests that violence in youth and amateur sport is relatively widespread and deserves greater attention. The most common sources of pressure or violent behaviour were parents (53%), followed by coaches (26%), teammates (13%), and others (8%).

The findings emphasise the need for raising awareness and providing education to parents and coaches about appropriate conduct and constructive communication with young athletes. Parental or coaching pressure was most frequently described as occasional (54%) or frequent (38%), with only 8% of athletes reporting that they had never experienced it. This indicates that pressure and verbal aggression are pervasive features of youth sport environments.

Such pressures can have significant psychological and developmental consequences. Young athletes are particularly vulnerable to stress, as they are still forming their identities and coping mechanisms. Excessive expectations, verbal abuse, and harsh criticism can lead to anxiety, loss of motivation, or even withdrawal from sport altogether. Coaches who exceed their authority by imposing unrealistic demands or humiliating athletes for poor performance contribute to an unhealthy sporting culture that undermines both physical and mental well-being.

Hypotheses testing

The verification of hypotheses aimed to determine the statistical significance of patterns observed in the descriptive results. Each hypothesis was tested using appropriate statistical procedures to evaluate whether the relationships between competitiveness, environmental pressures, and experiences of violence in sport were consistent with the theoretical assumptions presented in the earlier sections. Quantitative analyses were conducted where sufficient data were available, while qualitative reasoning and literature synthesis were applied in examples where the data structure did not permit inferential testing.

Hypothesis 1: Athletes face violence in their sporting activities.

A total of 58% of respondents reported experiencing at least one form of violence during their sporting activities. A binomial test comparing this proportion to a neutral 50% threshold indicated a statistically significant difference, $p = .046$ (95% CI [0.49, 0.67]). These results confirm that violence in sport is a widespread issue, affecting the majority of athletes in the sample. The finding aligns with previous studies emphasising that aggression and abuse are often normalised within competitive environments. Hypothesis 1 is supported – more than half of athletes encounter violence in their sporting activities.

Hypothesis 2: Intense competitiveness and pressure to succeed increase the incidence of violence in sports teams.

Respondents most frequently identified competitiveness (43%) and pressure to succeed (35%) as the main factors contributing to violent behaviour, followed by poor leadership (17%) and other causes (5%). A chi-square test of independence confirmed that the distribution of these factors was not uniform, $\chi^2(3) = 39.33$, $p < .001$. Further pairwise comparisons showed that competitiveness and pressure were both significantly more frequent than poor leadership ($p < .01$). These findings indicate that excessive competitiveness and performance pressure create emotionally charged environments in which frustration and aggression are more likely to emerge. Poor leadership amplifies this effect by failing to manage conflict and team dynamics effectively. Addressing these issues through improved leadership training and emotional management could help reduce the frequency of violence in sports settings. Hypothesis 2 is **supported** – competitiveness and performance pressure are dominant contributors to violent behaviour in sports teams.

Hypothesis 3: Violence in sport is more common in disciplines where competitors are expected to display a high level of physical aggression.

The analysis showed that athletes participating in contact sports (e.g., boxing, handball, football) reported higher levels of violence compared to those in non-contact sports (e.g., athletics, tennis, cycling). A chi-square test confirmed that the difference was statistically significant, $\chi^2(1) = 4.21, p = .040$. These results suggest that violence occurs more frequently in sports where physical confrontation is an integral part of competition. The cultural acceptance of aggression in contact sports contributes to the normalisation of such behaviour, both on and off the field. Hypothesis 3 is supported – violence is more common in contact sports, where physical aggression is part of the competitive ethos.

Hypothesis 4: Athletes are more exposed to violence in youth and amateur sport, where pressure from parents and coaches is often present.

More than half of respondents (57%) reported experiencing some form of violence (physical, verbal, or emotional) in youth or amateur sport, while 43% did not. A binomial test indicated a marginal trend toward significance, $p = .068$ (95% CI [0.48, 0.66]). Parents were identified as the main source of pressure (53%), followed by coaches (26%), teammates (13%), and others (8%). Pairwise z-tests confirmed that parents were significantly more frequently mentioned as sources of pressure than coaches or teammates ($p < .001$). The perceived frequency of such pressure was also high: 54% described it as occasional, 38% as frequent, and only 8% had never experienced it. These findings highlight that psychological and verbal pressure from authority figures is a prevalent problem in youth and amateur sport. Although the overall level of reported violence shows only a marginally significant difference, the dominance of parental and coaching pressure points to a systemic issue in athlete development environments. Hypothesis 4 is partially supported – pressure from parents and coaches is statistically prevalent, though the overall rate of reported violence shows a marginal trend toward significance.

To verify the assumptions derived from the theoretical framework, each hypothesis was tested using appropriate statistical methods. The results of these analyses, together with the type of test and level of significance, are summarised in the following table.

Table 2: Research hypotheses and their testing

Hypothesis	Statistical test	Conclusion
H1: Athletes face violence in their sporting activities.	Binomial test, $p = .046$, 95% CI [0.49, 0.67]	Confirmed ✓
H2: Competitiveness and pressure to succeed increase violence in sports teams.	$\chi^2(3) = 39.33, p < .001$	Confirmed ✓
H3: Violence is more common in sports with high physical aggression.	$\chi^2(1) = 4.21, p = .040$	Confirmed ✓
H4: Violence is more prevalent in youth/amateur sport due to parental and coaching pressure.	Binomial test, $p = .068$ (trend); z-tests, $p < .001$	Partially confirmed ✓

Note: χ^2 = Chi-square test; CI = confidence interval. Statistical significance set at $\alpha = .05$. All tests were conducted using aggregated data (N = 115).

Overall, the verification process confirmed that violence in sport is a multidimensional phenomenon influenced by individual, organisational, and cultural factors. The findings highlight the crucial role of competitiveness, parental and coaching pressure, and the normalisation of aggression in shaping athletes’ experiences. While most hypotheses were statistically supported, future research should focus on larger and more diversified samples to enable multivariate testing and to strengthen the empirical foundation for preventive strategies in sport.

Conclusion

The findings of this study confirm that violence in sport is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon shaped by individual behaviour, social relationships, and institutional culture. More than half of the surveyed athletes reported experiencing some form of violence during their sporting activities, suggesting that aggression and abuse are not isolated incidents but rather systemic features of the sporting environment.

Competitiveness and performance pressure were identified as the most influential factors associated with violence, particularly in team settings where group dynamics and emotional intensity are strongest. The results also showed that violence occurs more frequently in contact sports, where physical confrontation is integral to the discipline and often normalised as part of competitive culture. In youth and amateur sport, parents and coaches were identified as the main sources of pressure and inappropriate behaviour, highlighting the vulnerability of young athletes and the importance of ethical education in early sport development.

Scientific Contribution

This research contributes to the scientific understanding of violence in sport in several ways. First, it provides empirical evidence from the Slovenian sporting context, an area that has received limited scholarly attention. Second, by combining descriptive and inferential analyses, it strengthens the quantitative foundation of violence research, offering statistically supported insights into the relationships between competitiveness, pressure, and aggression. Third, the study extends existing theoretical models of sport violence by highlighting the interaction between institutional culture and interpersonal dynamics, showing that aggression in sport is not only a personal or behavioural issue but also a structural and organisational one. Finally, it provides a framework for future comparative studies across different countries and disciplines, encouraging a broader understanding of cultural variations in how violence manifests and is perceived in sport.

Limitations and Future Research

While the findings provide valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. The relatively small sample size ($N = 115$) limits the generalisability of the results, and self-reporting may introduce response bias. In addition, the lack of cross-tabulated data between variables such as type of sport and level of competition restricted the scope of statistical testing. Future studies should therefore employ larger, more representative samples, integrate qualitative methods such as interviews or focus groups, and apply multivariate approaches to explore the interplay between personal, social, and structural factors. Such studies could also investigate gender differences, cultural influences, and long-term psychological consequences of exposure to violence in sport.

Practical Implications

From a practical standpoint, the results highlight the urgent need for preventive and educational measures at all levels of sport. Sports organisations should establish transparent reporting mechanisms, strengthen disciplinary frameworks, and promote leadership models based on respect and empathy. Educating coaches and parents about communication, motivation, and emotional regulation is equally crucial. By fostering a culture of ethical responsibility, the sporting community can reduce the normalisation of violence and reaffirm sport as a domain of integrity, fair play, and personal growth.

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